

Evaluation of the Concepts of Social Control and Power

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-9, 2023, p. 01 – 21. - 0099-0001-2309-0101.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

CURRENT SCIENCE

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

"• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Article Application Date: 08.2023

Article Publication Date: 08. 2023

Article Type: Review

Bariş Çeltik, Phd.

St. Clements University

Political Science A.B.D. PhD

Orcid ID: 0009-0005-4101-9642

Assoc. Prof. Dr. **Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER**

(Orcid ID: 0000-0001-5896-2956)

University: St. Clements University

Department: Psychology

Title: Advisor

In this study, the definition of power and its sources will be discussed. It will be argued that power is not only exercised by official authorities and state institutions, but also in other centers of power such as civil society, the media and the private sector. In addition, the control mechanisms of the government, especially the effect of democratic control mechanisms such as the judiciary, parliamentary and press freedom will also be discussed. However, this study will focus on the concept of social control. Social control is a natural counter-power of power and refers to the control activities of the society against the power, either individually or organized. Within the framework of this study, the history, forms and mechanisms of social control will be discussed and the effects of non-governmental organizations, media and citizens on power will be investigated. In addition, the interaction between power and social control and its results will be evaluated. In this context, it will focus on the effects of social control on power, the effectiveness of control mechanisms, and how the power acts in the absence of social control.

In general, this study was written in order to better understand the relationship between power and social control, to discuss the control mechanisms necessary for a democratic society, and to offer suggestions for strengthening social control mechanisms.

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION: CONCEPTS OF SOCIAL CONTROL AND POWER

While the concepts of power and social control are related, it is important to note that they are different concepts. Those in power often use their influence to shape social control mechanisms in ways that reinforce their interests and priorities. For example, to maintain social control over its citizens, a government may use its power to create laws and policies that restrict certain behaviors or limit access to resources. However, social control mechanisms can also be used to challenge and resist those in power. For example, social movements and activism can be seen as efforts to challenge the mechanisms of social control established by those in power and to promote alternative norms and values. In this context, through protest, advocacy and organizing, social movements can mobilize people to challenge and resist the status quo and promote social change. Social control mechanisms can also be used to promote social justice and equality. For example, affirmative action policies can be used to ensure equal access to resources and opportunities for historically marginalized groups and to promote greater social inclusion. Similarly, public education and awareness-raising campaigns can be used to challenge discriminatory norms and promote greater understanding and acceptance of diversity. In general, power and social control are intertwined, as those in power often use social control mechanisms to maintain their position and protect their interests. Understanding the complex relationship between power and social control is essential for creating more just and equitable societies.

PURPOSE

This study, titled "Evaluation of the Concepts of Social Control and Power", is based on revealing the relationship between these two concepts and contributing to the goal of creating a more egalitarian and just life and social order. In this framework, the aim of this study is to provide a clearer understanding of the relationship between power and social control, to discuss

3

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

and interpret the control mechanisms necessary for a democratic society, and to offer useful suggestions for strengthening social control mechanisms.

METHOD

In this theoretically oriented study, since it is aimed to evaluate and reveal the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, these social phenomena are examined in depth. In this context, the theoretical analysis method is applied in the study, and if there is any problem that arises around the relationship established between these two concepts, it is ensured to evaluate it and develop solution suggestions to contribute to its solution.

1. HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPTS OF SOCIAL CONTROL AND POWER

Social control mechanisms are tools and institutions used to maintain order in human societies, to determine norms and to ensure that these norms are properly implemented. In this context, social control is a necessary element for maintaining social order and ensuring that individuals live in harmony with each other. However, the historical development of social control mechanisms is closely related to different periods of human history. Early human societies developed certain rules and norms for natural selection and survival. These rules were used to control and direct the behavior of other members of the society. Within the framework of this guidance, early societies were led by their leaders and shamans. These leaders used their power to control other members of society and encourage certain behaviors. Shamans were also used to control and regulate the beliefs and rituals of the society (Akdağ, 2015).

Ancient Greek and Roman periods were a time when social control mechanisms became more complex. During these periods, laws and systems of punishment were developed. Roman law, for example, still forms the basis of modern legal systems. Agora is an important part of social control mechanisms in ancient Greece. In this context, the Agora was used as a square where people gathered, discussed and made decisions. Here, the public could oppose and criticize the decisions of political leaders. Another mechanism is the popular assembly. In Ancient Greece, the popular assembly was one of the most fundamental mechanisms of social control. Another

CURRENT SCIENCE

element is that the assembly is a platform where the representatives of the people gather and political decisions are made. In addition, the jury system is an important part of the judicial system in Ancient Greece. Jury members elected by the people played an important role in ensuring justice in the judicial process.

In the ancient Roman period, the forum was the center of social control mechanisms. In this context, the forum was used as a square where the people gathered, made decisions and criticized political leaders. In addition, in Ancient Rome, the popular assembly was a platform where the representatives of the people gathered and made political decisions. The popular assembly had an important role in the governance of the Roman Empire. In Ancient Rome, the jury system is an important part of the judicial system. Jurors played an important role in ensuring justice in the judicial process. In addition, the senate in Ancient Rome was a platform where the representatives of the people gathered and made political decisions. The Senate had an important role in the administration of the Roman Empire (Batukan, 2020).

The medieval period is generally a period in which feudalism and the church are strong. Social control mechanisms are quite different in this period. Social control mechanisms are effective in areas where the church is active. In this period, the church is at the center of social and cultural life in Medieval Europe. The church was influential in every aspect of people's lives and functioned as an effective mechanism of social control. The influence of the church was felt especially in areas such as spiritual life, morality and ceremonial behavior. Punishments imposed by the church in the medieval period can also be counted among the mechanisms of social control. The Church imposed various sanctions to punish those who sinned. These sanctions included activities such as repentance, prayer, fasting, pilgrimage and religious service. The Church also imposed punishments such as isolation from society to ostracize those who sinned. Under feudalism, social control mechanisms generally operated at the local level. However, feudal lords, as landowners, had the responsibility to maintain social order. To fulfill these responsibilities, many feudal lords established their own laws and punishments in their territories. Therefore, social control mechanisms are limited to the jurisdiction of feudal lords. Medieval social control mechanisms are different from today's social control mechanisms, but social control mechanisms in this period functioned in accordance with the social structure and cultural values of the period.

2. STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF SOCIAL CONTROL AND POWER

Social control is the process by which members of a society control each other through their behavior, actions and words. It is a method used to ensure that they behave in accordance with certain norms and values of a society and to prevent inappropriate behavior. Social control is not based on the control of a formal authority, but is rather a voluntary and spontaneous process. Interactions between individuals, the enforcement of social rules and the consequences of unacceptable behavior contribute to this process.

Social control can take many different forms. For example, a group of people giving each other verbal warnings to discourage inappropriate behavior, people in a neighborhood paying attention to each other and reporting suspicious people, or giving feedback on their behavior through social media. These methods contribute to the maintenance of social norms, helping to create a more harmonious model of behavior in society as a whole. In addition to all these, internal control, which is an element of social control, is the method by which organizations or individuals control and manage their own affairs. In social control, internal control is used as a tool for individuals to monitor and control their own activities. The internal audit mechanisms of individuals and society check the compliance of society with its objectives, the accuracy and effectiveness of reporting and management processes. Internal audit also checks the compliance of activities within internal audit with laws, regulations and ethical standards (Bayram, 2019).

External control is a form of control that comes from outside society. It is carried out by governments, judicial systems, civil society organizations, the media and other institutions. External control is often used to punish members of society or to enforce regulations. Governments, however, use external control to enforce laws and ensure public safety. Judicial systems also use external control to prosecute and punish criminals. Civil society organizations use external control to raise awareness about environmental pollution, human rights violations and other social problems, and to monitor regulatory agencies. The media use external monitoring to hold governments and other institutions accountable to public opinion. External oversight is an important part of the social control system and plays an important role in maintaining order and fairness in society, but in some cases, external oversight institutions can

CURRENT SCIENCE

also be abused or used for vested interests. Therefore, in addition to internal control mechanisms, external control institutions need to be audited and held accountable. Power, however, refers to a specific authority held by a person, institution or group. Power can be exercised in different spheres of a society, including political, economic, social, cultural and military spheres. Power relations in these spheres can determine social inequalities and discrimination and increase the control of certain groups over others. Social control and power are closely interrelated. Individuals, institutions or groups with power can control and direct other members of society (Çimen, 2020).

This control can be used to determine the behavior of individuals and increase social control. For example, political leaders use their power to determine and implement policies, while media outlets determine whether certain behaviors are acceptable in society. In all these ways, social control and power play an important role in the functioning of a society. These concepts are used to decide whether certain behaviors are acceptable or not in society.

Economic systems are one of the most important structural elements of power in any society. In capitalist systems, for example, those with more wealth and economic resources often have more power and influence over decision-making. This can take various forms, such as political lobbying, campaign contributions or institutional control over media outlets. In contrast, in socialist or communist systems, the state may have more control over economic resources, which can limit the power of private individuals or companies, but this can also lead to the concentration of power in the hands of the state or the ruling party, which can have its own negative consequences. The structure of a society's political system also has a profound impact on the distribution of power. Democracies, for example, distribute power more equally among citizens through voting and representation. However, even in democratic systems, some groups may have access to more power than others. For example, wealthy individuals or those with connections to political elites have more influence in decision-making than ordinary citizens. In another example, in authoritarian regimes, power is often concentrated in the hands of a single person or ruling party, which can lead to widespread human rights abuses and a lack of accountability. In hybrid political systems, such as those found in some countries in the developing world, power can be distributed among multiple elements, including traditional

7

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

authorities, religious leaders and military authorities. Social hierarchies, such as those based on race, gender or class, are another important structural element of power. In societies with strong social hierarchies, those in privileged or powerful positions often have greater access to resources and decision-making power (Demircan, 2019).

This can take various forms, such as discriminatory policies, limited educational opportunities or restricted access to political or economic power. However, efforts to challenge or disrupt social hierarchies can be an important tool for promoting social justice and equality. This can include policies aimed at addressing historical injustices, such as affirmative action programs, or efforts to challenge cultural norms and values that reinforce existing power imbalances. Cultural norms and values also play an important role in shaping the distribution of power within a society. For example, a culture that values individualism may prioritize the rights and freedoms of individuals over collective social welfare. For example, a culture that values male leadership may limit women's access to political or economic power, while a culture that values gender equality may prioritize women's participation in these areas.

Last but not least, legal systems are another important structural element of power. Laws and regulations can reinforce power structures and their enforcement can disproportionately affect certain groups or individuals. For example, laws criminalizing drug use can disproportionately affect low-income individuals or communities of color, while laws criminalizing same-sex relationships can disproportionately affect LGBTQ+ individuals. Efforts to reform or challenge legal systems are an important tool to promote social justice and equality. Whether this includes efforts to reform criminal justice systems, challenge discriminatory laws or policies, or promote legal frameworks that prioritize human rights and social welfare, it will benefit the good functioning of the legal system (Dolgun, 2003).

Power and social control are two interrelated concepts that are central to understanding how societies function. Power refers to the ability of individuals or groups to influence others or control resources. This can take many forms, from physical power and economic resources to social status and cultural norms. Those who hold power often have the ability to shape social norms, institutions and policies and use these mechanisms to maintain their position and protect their interests. Social control refers to the mechanisms and practices that societies use to regulate behavior and ensure compliance with social norms and values. These mechanisms can include

8

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

formal institutions such as laws and regulations as well as informal mechanisms such as social pressure and norms. The purpose of social control is to maintain social order and stability and to ensure that individuals behave in ways that are acceptable and appropriate to the wider society.

3. DEMOCRATIC FUNCTIONING AND MECHANISMS OF SOCIAL CONTROL

Public scrutiny is the process by which society exercises control over a particular institution, political party or individual. In a democratic society, public scrutiny enables the public to influence the activities of elected representatives and public institutions. Therefore, public scrutiny has an important place in a democratic society.

The functioning and mechanisms of social control in a democratic society can take many forms. The first of these is elections. Elections are one of the most fundamental tools for social control in a democratic society. Voters choose their representatives through elections and have a direct influence on the activities of their representatives. In the process of social control, elections enable voters to exercise their right to determine administrators by voting and to participate in decisions about public services by choosing the administrator of their choice. Another element is the media. The media is one of the most effective instruments of social control in society. The media inform the public, form public opinion and critically evaluate political events, decisions and practices. In this context, the media contributes to the process of social control by covering political events impartially. Another element is civil society organizations (Kavuş, 2009).

Civil society organizations have an important role in social control. These organizations deal with social problems, form public opinion, evaluate policies and make recommendations. In this context, civil society organizations work to protect the interests of the public in public services. In a democratic society, oversight mechanisms are independent institutions established to exercise oversight over public administration. These include the judicial system, accountability mechanisms, audit institutions and independent civilian oversight organizations. Audit mechanisms monitor the activities of the public administration, detect errors and ensure that the public interest is protected.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The judicial system plays a vital role in resolving disputes between individuals, organizations and government agencies. This includes civil and criminal cases brought before the courts for resolution through the application of the law. In this context, the judicial system helps to prevent violence, vigilantism and other forms of conflict resolution that can be destructive to society by providing a neutral forum for parties to resolve their disputes. In addition, the judicial system is responsible for the protection of individual rights and freedoms. This includes ensuring that the rights guaranteed by the constitution and other laws are respected and protected by state institutions and private individuals. In this case, the courts have the power to annul laws that violate individual rights and to hold government officials accountable for violating those rights. In addition, the judicial system acts as a check on the legislative and executive branches of government. It can overturn laws that are unconstitutional or violate individual rights (Mora, 2008).

It is also able to interpret laws enacted by the legislature and the executive to ensure their fair and consistent application. Furthermore, the judicial system promotes transparency and accountability by requiring court proceedings to be open to the public. This helps to ensure that justice is administered fairly and impartially and that courts are not influenced by external forces. The judicial system promotes the rule of law by ensuring that individuals and organizations are held accountable for their actions. This includes enforcing contracts, protecting property rights and punishing those who break the law. By upholding the rule of law, the judicial system helps to prevent lawlessness and chaos by promoting stability and order in society. Overall, the judicial system is a critical oversight mechanism that helps to maintain order in society, protect individual rights, promote transparency and uphold the rule of law.

Accountability mechanisms in society are designed to hold individuals or institutions accountable for their actions and decisions. These mechanisms can be approached in many different ways. For example, an audit is the process of examining an individual's or organization's financial records, performance measures or other data to ensure that they are acting in accordance with established rules and regulations. Performance evaluations, on the other hand, are assessments of an individual's or organization's performance, usually conducted by independent third parties. They can be used to determine whether the individual or organization has achieved predetermined goals and objectives.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Control mechanisms are designed to regulate or influence behavior, usually through the exercise of authority or power. Within these mechanisms, laws and regulations are rules established by governments or other institutions to govern behavior. These rules are usually enforced through legal action. Monitoring and oversight, however, involves the regular review of an individual's or organization's activities to ensure that they are acting in accordance with established rules and regulations. Sanctions and penalties can also be used to deter individuals or organizations from engaging in certain behaviors. These can include fines, suspensions or other disciplinary actions (Sucu, 2011).

Audit institutions are organizations responsible for conducting independent audits of public entities such as government agencies and non-profit organizations. They are usually established by governments and are tasked with ensuring that public entities use public resources effectively and efficiently. The primary role of audit institutions is to conduct audits to assess whether public organizations are acting in accordance with relevant laws and regulations, using resources effectively and achieving their objectives. They can also provide advisory services to help organizations improve their management practices and processes. In this context, audit institutions can perform different types of audits, including financial audits, performance audits and compliance audits. In addition, by providing independent oversight of public organizations, audit institutions help to improve transparency and accountability in government and public organizations. Audit institutions help promote good governance by ensuring that public bodies are accountable for their actions and use public resources effectively and efficiently. In this context, the work of audit institutions helps to build trust and confidence in public institutions, which is essential for a healthy democracy.

Civilian audit organizations can be independent from the control mechanisms in society, but their independence can be affected by a variety of factors such as their funding sources, legal powers and relationships with other organizations. Civilian oversight bodies are nongovernmental organizations that conduct audits of government agencies and other organizations to ensure transparency, accountability and effective use of public resources. They play a critical role in promoting good governance, fighting corruption and improving the delivery of public services. To be truly independent, civilian audit organizations need to be free from any influence or control by government agencies or other organizations they audit. This

CURRENT SCIENCE

includes freedom to choose which organizations to audit, access to all relevant information, and the ability to publish their findings without fear of reprisals. To maintain independence, civilian oversight organizations often rely on funding sources independent of the government agencies or organizations they oversee. This can include funding from private foundations, individual donors or international organizations. By diversifying funding sources, civilian audit organizations can reduce the risk of being influenced or controlled by any one organization or government agency. In addition to funding sources, civilian audit organizations need to have a strong legal mandate that protects their independence and ensures that they have the legal authority to conduct audits and publish their findings. This includes having access to all relevant information and the ability to interview key stakeholders and hold public hearings. In general, civilian audit organizations need to maintain their independence by avoiding conflicts of interest and maintaining impartiality (Yücedağ, 2017).

This should include avoiding any relationship or partnership with the organizations they oversee and ensuring that their staff and leadership have no personal or financial interests in the organizations they oversee. In light of all this, civilian oversight organizations can be independent of the control mechanisms in society, but they need to have the right sources of funding, legal powers and relationships to maintain their independence and ensure that they can effectively perform the functions of state institutions.

4. POLITICAL POWER, SOCIAL FORCES AND THE FUNCTIONING OF THE STATE WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE ROLE AND IMPACT OF SOCIAL CONTROL

Social control is the process by which a society monitors, evaluates and criticizes the activities of political power and the state. In this process, individuals, civil society organizations, media and other stakeholders strive to monitor, criticize and influence the activities and policies of the state. In addition, social scrutiny ensures that the functioning of political power and the state is open and transparent. Thus, political power and the state are able to develop and implement policies in line with the demands of society. Social scrutiny influences the policies of the political power and the state, while at the same time increasing public trust. There are different

CURRENT SCIENCE

ways of social control. These can include the media, local governments and other stakeholders. All of these mechanisms play an important role in monitoring, evaluating and criticizing the activities of political power and the state.

One of the most fundamental roles of the media in social control is to inform the public. The media provide a platform for sharing information about current events, political issues, social problems and more. This information can help people stay informed and informed about important issues that affect their lives and communities. When people are well informed, they are better equipped to hold those in power accountable and make informed decisions. However, another important role of the media in social control is to expose abuse and hold those in power accountable. For example, investigative journalism can expose corruption, abuse of power and other forms of abuse (Akdağ, 2015).

When the media reports on these issues, it can lead to public outrage and pressure for change. By drawing attention to these issues, the media can help prevent the abuse of power and encourage those in power to act more accountably and ethically. With all this, the media has the power to frame issues in ways that influence public opinion and policy. By choosing which news stories to cover and how to present them, the media can shape public perceptions and attitudes towards various issues. For example, media coverage of protests or demonstrations can frame these events either as legitimate expressions of dissent or as violent and disruptive disruptions of the social order.

The way the media frames these events can influence how the public reacts and ultimately shape public policy. Above all, the media can stimulate public debate and discussion on important issues by providing a platform for different perspectives and viewpoints to be heard. This can be particularly important in a democracy where citizens are expected to engage in informed debate and dialog on key policy issues. In this context, by providing a platform for information, analysis and debate, the media can help promote informed and participatory citizenship. Finally, the media can promote transparency and accountability by reporting on government activities and holding public officials accountable for their actions. By shining a light on government activities, the media can help prevent abuse of power and promote a more open and accountable government. For example, investigative journalists can report on cases of government waste, fraud or abuse, which can lead to public pressure for reforms and more responsible government

13

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

practices. It is important to note, however, that the media's role in social control is not without its challenges. The media can be subject to various forms of influence and control, including government censorship, corporate ownership and pressure from interest groups.

These factors can limit the media's ability to function as an effective control mechanism in society. In addition, media coverage can sometimes be sensationalized or biased, further undermining its role as a reliable source of information and analysis, but despite these challenges, the media remains an important tool for promoting social control and accountability in democratic societies.

Within the framework of social control, local authorities are responsible for ensuring that residents in their jurisdiction comply with local laws and regulations. One way of doing this is through law enforcement. Local governments often have their own police departments responsible for enforcing local laws and regulations. In this context, police officers may be responsible for responding to emergencies, conducting investigations and making arrests. Local governments have law enforcement elements responsible for ensuring that residents comply with building and zoning laws, as well as other regulations related to property maintenance and public health. These entities can issue citations or fines to residents who violate these rules and can take legal action if violations are not addressed. Local governments are also responsible for issuing licenses and permits for various activities, including commercial activities, construction projects and events (Çimen, 2020).

By regulating these activities, local governments can exert a degree of control over the behavior of residents and businesses within their jurisdiction. For example, local governments may require businesses to obtain licenses to operate within the community. These licenses may be subject to certain conditions or requirements, such as regular inspections or compliance with local zoning regulations. Local governments also play a role in promoting public health and safety. As part of social control, local governments can provide health services, regulate food and water safety, and ensure that buildings and structures are safe and in compliance with the law. Local governments may also be responsible for emergency management and response efforts, such as coordinating responses to natural disasters or other emergencies. In general, local governments have a range of tools and resources at their disposal to implement social

CURRENT SCIENCE

control within their jurisdiction. While the specific strategies and methods used may vary depending on the community, the efforts of effective social control mechanisms are necessary to maintain order, improve public safety and ensure compliance with local laws and regulations.

As mentioned earlier under other stakeholders in social audits, civil society organizations are non-governmental organizations working to promote social and environmental justice. They can play a critical role in social audits by mobilizing communities, conducting surveys and research, and advocating for the implementation of recommendations arising from social audits. They can also help ensure that social audits are inclusive and participatory by engaging with marginalized and vulnerable groups and providing a platform for their voices to be heard (Kavuş, 2009).

Citizen participation is a critical component of social audits. Citizens can provide feedback on the performance of public institutions and programs, highlight areas of concern and propose solutions. They can also hold public officials accountable for their actions and advocate for better service delivery. In this context, citizen participation in social audits helps to strengthen democracy and improve transparency and accountability in government. Academics can also contribute to social audits by conducting research on public institutions and programs, analyzing data and making recommendations for improvements. They can also provide training and capacity building to stakeholders involved in social audits. In this context, academics help ensure that social audits are evidence-based and rigorous and generate meaningful insights into the performance and impact of public institutions and programs. In addition, the private sector can be a stakeholder in social audits, particularly where public-private partnerships are involved.

Elements of the private sector can contribute to social audits by providing technical expertise, funding and other resources to support the assessment of public entities and programs. Private sector engagement in social audits can help align public institutions and programs with the needs and priorities of the private sector and deliver social and economic benefits for all stakeholders. Overall, taking all this information into account, social audits involve multiple stakeholders working together to ensure the accountability, transparency and effectiveness of public institutions and programs. By engaging a wide range of constituencies, community audits

CURRENT SCIENCE

can generate more comprehensive and meaningful insights into the performance and impact of public institutions and programs and help improve service delivery and increase public trust in government.

5. POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL CONTROL AND POWER

In the context of the positive effects of public scrutiny, political power and the functioning of the state, this relationship is a powerful tool for promoting accountability in government. Through independent audits and evaluations of government programs and services, those with a mechanism for public scrutiny can identify areas of inefficiency, waste and corruption. This information can then be used to hold public officials accountable for their actions and promote greater transparency and accountability in government. In addition, when political leaders and the state support social scrutiny, they can create a culture of accountability in government that encourages public officials to act in the public interest and use public resources responsibly. This can help build public trust in government and ensure that citizens are confident that their elected officials are working in their best interests. In addition, public scrutiny can encourage citizens to become more involved in the political process and take an active role in holding elected officials accountable (Çimen, 2020).

By providing information about government programs and services, public scrutiny can help citizens understand how their government works and how they can have an impact on decisions that affect their lives. When political leaders and the state support public scrutiny and encourage citizen participation, they can create a more vibrant democracy where citizens feel empowered to shape the decisions that affect them. This can lead to a stronger sense of civic engagement and a greater sense of ownership over decisions made by government. In addition, public scrutiny can help reduce corruption in government by exposing fraud or abuse of power.

In general, social control, political power and state functioning are interlinked and can have positive effects on each other. By supporting social control and fostering strong political leadership and effective state institutions, governments can promote accountability, improved governance, citizen participation, reduced corruption and improved service delivery.

CURRENT SCIENCE

In the context of negative impacts, social audit is a powerful tool to promote transparency and accountability in government. It involves an independent review of government programs and services by citizens and civil society organizations to assess their impact, efficiency and effectiveness, but it can be difficult for citizens to conduct meaningful social auditing if government agencies are not transparent in their operations or finances. Lack of transparency can also lead to corruption and inefficiency, which can undermine the effectiveness of government programs and services. Furthermore, political power is the ability of individuals or groups to influence government decision-making. Lack of transparency and accountability in government can weaken political power by limiting access to information and decision-making (Mora, 2008).

This can make it difficult for citizens or civil society organizations to participate in government decision-making and influence policies that affect their lives. In this context, lack of public participation can also lead to reduced trust in the government and reduced confidence in the state's ability to provide basic services. In this context, the functioning of the state can also be negatively affected by a lack of transparency, accountability and public participation. Without transparency, it is therefore difficult to identify and address inefficiencies or corruption in state institutions. This can lead to a lack of trust in government and reduced confidence in the state's ability to provide basic services and support economic development. Lack of public participation can make it difficult for state institutions to identify and respond to the needs and concerns of their constituents, further reducing trust in the state. Overall, a lack of transparency, accountability and public participation has serious negative impacts on social control, political power and the functioning of the state. It is essential that governments promote transparency and accountability in their operations and decision-making processes and engage with citizens and civil society organizations to ensure that government activities are open, accessible and responsive to the needs and concerns of their constituents.

6. THE ROLE OF DEMOCRACY IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL CONTROL AND POWER

The relationship between social control and democracy is close. The essence of democracy is that those in power are elected by the people, but in the exercise of power, sometimes those in power can act in their own self-interest and this can lead to a loss of public trust. Social control mechanisms are therefore crucial for the healthy functioning of democracy. These mechanisms make those in power accountable by monitoring and criticizing their behavior and decisions. In this way, public trust is regained and those in power are forced to act in accordance with public demands.

The importance of social control mechanisms for democracy has been historically proven. For example, the freedom of the press and freedom of expression movements in England in the 18th century, the development of civil society organizations that monitor the government, and the existence of elected representatives of the people are considered to be the basic elements of democracy. Moreover, in modern democracies, social control mechanisms have developed further. Freedom of the press, social media, labor unions, academics, lawyers, civil society organizations and other groups play an important role in monitoring power. However, the importance of social control mechanisms for democracy is not limited to monitoring the activities of the government. Increased opportunities for the public to participate in power are also part of social control. This ensures that the people are involved in political decision-making and that the government pays more attention to the demands of the people. With all this in mind, public scrutiny is vital for the healthy functioning of democracy. By monitoring and criticizing the activities of the government, these mechanisms enable the public to influence the government and ensure that the government takes into account the demands of the public (Batukan, 2020).

CURRENT SCIENCE

CONCLUSION

Social control and power are two intertwined concepts that play an important role in shaping the functioning of societies in general. Social control refers to the various mechanisms and practices that societies use to regulate behavior and maintain social order. These mechanisms can take many forms, including laws, norms, values and institutions.

Power, on the other hand, can be exercised by groups or institutions and used to achieve a wide range of goals, from personal gain to broader social change. The relationship between social control and power is complex and multifaceted. In this context, social control mechanisms can be used to reinforce existing power structures and maintain the status quo. For example, laws and regulations can be used to protect the interests of those in power, while norms and values can be used to legitimize those in positions of authority.

Power can also be used to shape social control mechanisms and influence the way they are implemented. Those in power can use their influence to promote certain norms, values and laws that align with their interests, while suppressing those that do not. For example, powerful individuals or groups may seek to promote certain moral codes or religious beliefs that align with their worldview while marginalizing alternative viewpoints. However, it is important to recognize that the relationship between social control and power is not always negative. Social control mechanisms can be used to promote positive social change and protect the rights of marginalized groups.

For example, laws and regulations can be used to promote gender equality or protect the rights of minority groups. In conclusion, the relationship between social control and power is complex and multifaceted, and its effects on individuals and society are significant. In order to create a more just and equitable society, it is important to critically examine how power is exercised and the ways in which mechanisms of social control are deployed. In doing so, the creation of an order in which all individuals are treated with dignity, respect and justice, and power is used to promote the common good rather than reinforce existing hierarchies, will be good for all.

CURRENT SCIENCE

RESTRICTION

In this study, which is built around a better understanding of the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, the boundaries of these two concepts are determined and this evaluation is carried out with the information provided from the sources obtained by taking into account the scope of the research. This study is globally limited to the scientific studies on the subject.

NOTICES

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external experts.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Financial Support: The author did not report any financial support for the study.

ETHICS DECLARATION

The publication ethics of this journal; It is a scientific journal in the field of social sciences that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with the main criteria specified as openness, honesty, respect for the findings and work of other publishers and objectivity.

REFERENCES

Akdag, G. Gözetim Toplumu Teorilerinin Tarihsel ve Teorik Bir İncelemesi, Adnan Menderes University, Master's Thesis, 2015.

Bal, N. "*Social Control or Forms of Bio-Power: Sociological Evaluation of Covid-19 Disease*", Volume: 4, Issue: 1, pp. 42 - 55, 2022.

- Batukan, C. "A Foucauldian Perspective on the Forms of Power of the XXI. Century", Journal of Education Science Society, Vol. 18, No. 69, pp. 1 - 40, 2020.
- Bayrakci, O. and Caglayan, S. "Control of Labor as a Mechanism of Social Control: From Taylorism to Ideological Control", Journal of Management and Economics Research, pp.5 - 23, 2018.
- Bayram, T. İktidar ve İnternet: A Siberetic Approach to Digital Control and Surveillance Mechanisms, Hacettepe University, Master's Thesis, 2019.
- Biber, A. and Turancı, E. "The Social Devil's Triangle: Power, Hegemony and Propaganda", Akdeniz İletişim Dergisi, Issue: 21, pp. 1 - 14, 2014.
- Bulut, N. Political Power Types and (Modern) State as a Political Type, cdn.istanbul.edu.tr/FileHandler2.ashx?f=siyasal-iktidar-tipleri-ve-bir-siyasal-tipi-olarakmodern-devlet.pdf, Access Date: 04.08.2023.
- Çimen, Ü. "A Dystopian Approach to the Relationship between Power and Technology: Kent Güvenlik Yönetim Sistemi Merkezleri Eleştirisi", Kafkas University Journal of Institute of Social Sciences, Spring 2020, Issue: 25, pp. 219 - 240, 2020.
- Demircan, G. Gözetim Ve Gözetimin Toplumsal Legitimiyeti Üzerine Bir İnceleme, Ekin Kitabevi, Bursa, 2019.
- Dolgun, U. Gözetim Toplumu: A Sociological Approach to Information Technologies and Surveillance, Istanbul University, PhD Thesis, 2003.
- Karakas, M. "Science and Sociology in terms of Power Relations", Journal of Social Sciences, Vol. 4, No.
- Kavuş, S. Bilgi-İktidar İlişkisi Çerçevinde Bilgi Edinme Hakkı, Ankara University, Master's Thesis, 2009.
- Mora, N. "Media, Society and Symbolic Elites as News Sources", International Journal of Human Sciences, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 1 - 25, 2008.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Sucu, I. "*The Counter Utopia Face of Surveillance Society: Power Forces and Others*", Atatürk Journal of Communication, Vol: 2, pp. 1 - 16, 2011.

Yucedag, I. "*Control Assemblage in Modern Society*", SDÜ Faculty of Arts and Sciences Journal of Social Sciences, August 2017, Issue: 41, pp. 161-175, 2017.